

Influence of structural determinants on performance and survival: case of Russian universities

Angelika Tsivinskaya¹[0000-0002-3261-7393]

¹ European University at Saint Petersburg, Saint Petersburg 191187, Russia
atsivinskaya@eu.spb.ru

Abstract. Since 2006, Russian government made energetic attempts to boost academic performance of the country's universities, to shut down underperforming institutions and to turn the survivors into world-class schools. Overall, the organizational population of the Russian HEIs shrank by some 40% as a result of these efforts. Since 2012, Russian policies in the higher education sphere were largely directed by the results of the Survey of efficiency of higher education organizations – a set of quantitative performance indicators used to sort efficient from non-efficient organizations. In this paper we use statistical methods to, first, look into the structural factors which influence certain schools' success in the Survey, and second, analyze the consequences of implemented performance evaluation system on survival rates for certain groups of universities.

Keywords: Higher Education, Survival Analysis, Universities, Evaluation, Performance, KPIs.

1 Introduction

In Russia, as well as in many other countries, university governance has recently evolved in the direction of market-oriented model (Dobbins et al., 2011) which presumes distributing a significant share of funding on the basis of key performance indicators (KPIs).

The ultimate rationale of the introduction of the Survey was the strife to make Russian universities sources of marketable innovations and national soft power. It is widely believed that what they need to achieve this objective is efficient management which is the key to transforming nearly any HEI into a world leading research university. Characteristically, the Survey is called “the Survey of Efficiency” implying that what is distinguishing its leaders from outsiders is the ability to use their resources, rather than the amount and character of the resources available.

However, as the data of the survey demonstrate focusing the reformers' attention on personalities of higher administrators diverts it from other variables influencing a university's trajectory. Factors other than a higher administrator's skills and motivation are necessary for explaining why a given university has occupied a particular niche in the higher education ecology. Moreover, their results in each of the main indicators

were strongly predicating on various structural characters of the position of the university in the higher education system.

In the first part we focus on showing how structural determinants such as region, profile of universities and others influence performance (six KPIs). In the second part of our paper we show results of existing policy on survival of universities and to the question of “Is the existing survey identify inefficient universities or serves only political agenda to eliminate selected group of universities?”

2 Data

The main data used in this paper is obtained from the Efficiency monitoring initiated by the Ministry of Education in Russia which results is available online (<http://indicators.miccedu.ru/monitoring/>). We used data collected from 2014 to 2017 for 822 universities and 979 branch campuses. We mainly used subset of data only for universities excluding branches branch campuses.

Additionally, we collected from other sources some information, such as, demographic, economic and migration statistics by region, typologies of regional economies from Russian Statistical Agency.

3 Methods

In first part we focus on showing descriptive statistics and statistical tests to show differences in the performance for groups of universities. Our hypotheses, based on previous analysis (Sokolov, 2017) were that the whole trajectory of a university’s evolution was heavily determined by its “ascriptive” or “inborn” characteristics. We had several classes of independent variables or factors determining its getting into one of the niches, such as (a) if it was public or private; (b) if it was localized in a bigger city or a wealthy region, (c) its nominal profile or “family”.

In the second part of our research we showed the consequences of implementation of current evaluation system using survival analysis techniques to estimate “survival” for different groups of universities. For this purpose, we mainly applied nonparametric method of Kaplan-Meier estimates.

4 Results

4.1 Performance

Our analysis shows that performance is highly influenced by the factor if a university is a branch campus. For all KPIs they have shown inferior results compare to main universities. Profile of universities is also influence performance, especially difficult to be efficient for private ones (only 47 % were efficient, comparing to classical state – 92.8 %). We also found out that location of university in the regional capital attracts students with higher scores in unified state exam and employment rates are also higher.

4.2 Survival

What were the consequences of implementing efficiency metrics not taking into account structural variables which influence a university's performance? Our data demonstrate that such KPI's discriminated against specific groups of universities. Survival curves for universities from 2014 to 2017 demonstrate that private universities and branches in minor cities were among the major victims (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Survival curves based on Kaplan-Meier estimate.

5 Summary

Overall, it seems that choosing a set of performance indicators without enough regard to the structural sources of variation results in the survival of the best positioned, rather than the fittest or the most efficient. An old sociological wisdom says that a fair competition among unequal participants just increases the gap and serves only to legitimize the winner's advantage. Without considering the role of these factors, allocation of resources on the bases of universal formal criteria which is practiced in Russia now would inevitably lead to polarization of the higher education system and to degradation of the schools which were initially lacking "inborn" characters essential for success.

References

1. Dobbins M., Knill C., Vögtle E. M.: An analytical framework for the cross-country comparison of higher education governance. *Higher Education* 62(5), 665-683 (2011).
2. Sokolov M. M.: Mif ob universitetskoi strategii ekonomicheskie nishi i organizacionnie kareri rossiiskih vuzov. *Voprosi obrazovaniya*. [Journal of Educational Studies] 2, 36-73 (2017).